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Review/reflexion

REVIEW OF THE BOOK
PSYCHOTIC DISORDERS IN MONTENEGRO:
FINDINGS FROM THE IMPULSE STUDY

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Psychotic disorders in Montenegro: Findings from the IMPULSE study is a monography that covers the main results from IMPULSE study obtained by the Montenegrin team, written by Prof. Lidija Injac Stevović and researchers Selman Repišti and Tamara Radojičić.

A helpful feature of this book is its division into three main sections (Introduction, Methodology, Results) with 16 subsections, and appendix with explanations of symbols, abbreviations and indexes of professional terms. In each section there is inclusion of explanatory comments or noteworthy results and suitable discussion.

The objective of the IMPULSE study is to facilitate the development of psychosocial care and treatment for people with psychotic disorders in Southeast Europe. The main clinical study within the project is one of the largest ever conducted randomized-controlled trials of a psychosocial

intervention with individuals with psychosis in five South – Eastern countries, among which is Montenegro. There are a small number of instruments that are applied in our area in the field of psychiatry, and which have been validated in our countries. The Montenegrin team tested the validity of these questionnaires in their local context and demonstrated their applicability in everyday clinical practice. It thus laid the foundations for further successful research in this field where objectification or RDoC (Research Domain Criteria) is the goal that the entire world psychiatric science strives to achieve. The book covers result from all questionnaires and clinical scales about demographic characteristics, quality of life, and symptoms in patients taking part to the project. Precisely, it is about BPRS-E, BSI, ReQoL, MANSA, and CSQ-8 questionnaires.

The monograph is a great blend of psychometric science and clinical application. The interdisciplinary, collaborative and partnership research process implemented in the monography will contribute to higher quality of results, exchanging ideas across disciplines, and bridging the gap between research, policy, and practice in this part of the Balkans. As a result, I hope the

monography outputs will be sustainable for further mutual activities between clinicians, researchers, commissioners and policy makers.

The results described in this book could be used for investigating the local context and for improving the policies about conditions of people suffering with psychosis and overcoming financial barriers encountered in the treatment of psychosis in the Montenegro.

I see this book as initial standard, incorporating several interesting and worthwhile contributions for those working primarily on research of a psychosocial interventions in individuals with psychosis. This book will be a valuable text for clinicians, including psychiatrists, psychologists, psychotherapists, physicians, social workers, service users, family members and policy makers. It will also be of great interest to academics and students.

The value of this work was undoubtedly contributed by the great personal professional knowledge and experience of the authors in this field of psychiatric medicine. Between the covers of this book are professional papers, studiously written at an enviable level with the help of rich and well-chosen professional literature stating the innovations, but also with an enviable empirical dowry of the authors themselves.

It could be said that Montenegrin psychiatry does not lag behind the world trends, which is at the same time a guarantee that the current and future generations of clinicians will fulfill their diagnostic and therapeutic role of the most serious psychiatric diseases.

I hope that this monograph will be the neuronal excitatory “impulse” to the development of research in non-pharmacological mental health care not only in Montenegro, but also in the whole region of Southeast Europe.

I would like to thank my colleagues, the authors of this monography, for the successfully completed research, for ideas and concise thoughts and results, and I wish them many more successes in this field which will develop even more and more in our countries.

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